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Arthropods of the Limarí basin (Coquimbo region, Chile): agricultural importance in agricultural ecosystems

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Abstract

Arthropods are an important group of organisms in agricultural ecosystems due to their ecological impact as pollinators and agents of natural pest control. Some species, however, may damage crops and be vectors for diseases or reservoirs of zoonoses that may affect human populations. The economic impact of arthropods may be a limiting factor of production and development in fragile and vulnerable ecosystems, as is the case of the Limarí basin in the Coquimbo region – an important agricultural area within the semiarid region of Chile. In view of the limited amount of information available about potential pests and natural enemies of the main crops cultivated in the Limarí Valley, we analyzed the agricultural importance of arthropods in the Limarí basin. After reviewing historical data, specimen collections, and the literature, a total of 412 arthropods species of agricultural importance were recorded, 92.5% of them insects and the rest (31 species) arachnids. Around 25% of the species were quarantined species in foreign markets, and 21.8% were species that may have a positive impact on agriculture. Within Insecta, the genera *Aleurothrixus*, *Trialeurodes* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), and *Pseudococcus* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) were the main groups associated to agricultural crops containing species of quarantine importance for foreign markets. We hope that this species inventory serves as a basis for identifying biological vulnerabilities in a basin, which has seen a continuous expansion of productive land in recent years.

Keywords: agricultural pests, arid zones, Limari valley, quarantine species, transverse valleys, Chile.

INTRODUCTION

The significance of arthropods for agricultural production systems lies in their ecological role as pollinators and natural pest controllers (Naranjo *et al.*, 2015). However, the majority of arthropod species are harmful agents that damage crops – potentially reducing its productivity – or attack stored products (Elgueta, 1993; Artigas, 1994). Arthropods can also be vectors and reservoirs of zoonotic agents or behave as ectoparasites, with severe economic losses to cattle-raising systems and direct consequences to human health (Canals and Cattán, 2006). For these reasons, controlling arthropod pests in products destined for export is critical, since many of these pests are of quarantine significance in certain destination markets (e.g., the US) (Follett and Neven, 2006).

The Norte Chico area in semiarid Chile extends from 27° to 32° S, encompassing the Atacama and Coquimbo regions. This area is characterized by the presence of an intermediate depression interspersed with mountain ranges that give origin to transverse valleys that extend from the Andes to the Pacific Ocean (DGA, 1986). In the Norte Chico, the valleys of Copiapó (27-28° S) and Huasco (28-29° S) in the Atacama region and the valleys of Elqui (30° S), Limarí (31° S) and Choapa (32° S) in the Coquimbo region form a

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semiarid matrix characterized by scarce and disperse precipitation and the presence of permanent, mixed regime rivers (Romero *et al.*, 1998).

Significant among these transverse valleys is the Limarí River basin, considered to be the most economically important food and agricultural center (INE, 2007), featuring secondary production activities such as small-scale agriculture, cattle raising and small-scale mining (Cortés, 2016). Nowadays the surface of the Limarí valley is covered by forage (25,456 ha), fruit (20,151 ha), grapevine (8,353 ha) and vegetable (4,753 ha) crop lands (INE, 2007).

Most of the agricultural production is destined for foreign markets (e.g., the US, Japan, Europe) subject to international phytosanitary requirements (FAO, 2000). The most economically important fruit crops include grapevines (7,321.7 ha), avocado trees (4,128.0 ha), olives (2,511.2 ha), and mandarin trees (1,573.4 ha) (INE, 2007; CIREN, 2015). Consequently, pest control is very important for agricultural exports since some arthropod species can severely affect the agricultural ecosystems' production and result in the products being rejected in their destination markets (Moore-Tello, 2009).

The economic impacts of the damage caused by arthropods are more severe in fragile and vulnerable ecosystems, such as the basins of semiarid Chile, particularly the Limarí basin, the most important agricultural area of the semiarid region of Chile (INE, 2007). The objective of this study was to document agriculturally important arthropod species in the Limarí River basin (Coquimbo Region, Chile).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study site

The study area comprised the three basins associated to, or influenced by, the Limarí River (Coquimbo Region, Chile), namely, the Limarí River basin itself, the coastal basin of the Elqui and Limarí rivers, and the coastal basin of the Limarí and Choapa rivers (Figure 1). The limits of these three basins were defined based on 1:250,000 maps (Shapefile) from the Instituto Geográfico Militar (IGM). The predominant soil types in the area are entisols, aridisols, and inceptisols, all of which show some influence from the vegetation (Morales, 2006). The climate is steppe type, ranging from steppe with abundant clouds in the coast to cold steppe in the mountainous areas (Novoa and López, 2001). The mean annual precipitation exceeds 300 mm in mountainous areas and reaches 60 mm to 240 mm in the lowlands near the coast (2001). The annual temperature is homogeneous in the coast, but varies in the interior valleys and mountainous areas (DMC, 2001). Far from the influence of the sea, the vegetation in the interior areas corresponds to an interior steppe scrubland (Gajardo, 1993; Squeo *et al.*, 2001).

Capture methods and data collection

To investigate the agricultural importance of arthropods in the Limarí basin, distributional data of arthropod species records was collected based on a review of reference material deposited in the following entomological collections: Juan Enrique Barriga Collection (JEBC); Laboratorio de Entomología Ecológica, Universidad de La Serena, La Serena, Chile (LEULS); and Museo Entomológico Luis Peña, Departamento de Sanidad Vegetal, Facultad de Ciencias Agronómicas, Universidad de Chile, Santiago, Chile (MEUC). Additionally, data from entomological prospectations conducted between 2009 and 2015 in the Limarí Province was provided by the Servicio Agrícola y Ganadero de Chile (SAG [Chilean Agricultural and Livestock Service]). Lastly, these records were supplemented with distributional data from the literature and data from manual prospectations and captures conducted using entomological nets and UV light between June and October of 2015. The captured material was cleaned, dried, and preserved in alcohol (80% for Acari and 70% for Insecta) until processing and mounting. All the collected material is deposited at the Laboratorio de Entomología Ecológica of Universidad de La Serena (LEULS). Acari was taxonomically identified based on Krantz (1978) and Rojas (2005), whereas Araneae was characterized following Ramírez (1999) and the World Spider Catalog (2020). Within Insecta, the taxonomic identification of Coleoptera followed Barriga

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(1990, 2020), Barriga *et al.* (1993), Elgueta and Marvaldi (2006), Vidal and Guerrero (2007), Solervicens (2014), Moore and Vidal (2015), González (2020); for Lepidoptera, Artigas (1994), Estay and Bruna (2002), Angulo *et al.* (2006); for Hemiptera, Ripa and Rodríguez (2000), Estay and Bruna (2002), Castro da Costa (2010); for Diptera, Estay and Bruna (2002); and for Hymenoptera, Rojas (2005).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 412 agriculturally important arthropods species were recorded in the study area, 92.5% (381 species) of them insects (Insecta) and only 7.5% arachnids (Tables 1 and 2).

Among arachnids, the mite *Panonychus citri* (McGregor) (Acari: Tetranychidae) was the main phytophagous species on citrus fruits, followed by *Brevipalpus chilensis* Baker (Acari: Tenuipalpidae) and *Oligonychus* sp. (Acari: Tetranychidae), the latter two phytophagous on fruit trees (Table 1). Of these species, the native *B. chilensis* is a pest of quarantine significance that causes severe economic damage to grapevine trees (González, 1989).

Within Insecta, the genera *Aleurothrixus*, *Trialeurodes* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae), and *Pseudococcus* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) were the main groups associated with agricultural fields (e.g., fruit trees, vegetables) in the Limarí basin (Table 2). Aleyrodidae is a group of insects associated with a large number of crops that can affect the plants' resilience due to their sap-sucking characteristics (Tello *et al.*, 2013). Among the species of quarantine significance for the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO), we recorded *Aleurothrixus floccosus* Maskell, *Aleurothrixus porteri* Quaintance & Baker, and *Aleurothrixus* sp. (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), phytophagous whiteflies on citrus trees, cucurbits, and nightshades (Table 2).

Another significant group in the Limarí basin is the family Pseudococcidae, one of the major phytosanitary problems for table grape exports in Chile as a result of their quarantine significance in several foreign markets (González, 2011). Some species, such as *Pseudococcus viburni* (Signoret), *Pseudococcus meridionalis* Prado, and *Pseudococcus cribata* González, are very common in Chilean vineyards (Correa *et al.*, 2012) and may affect the resilience of plants (Artigas, 1994) and transmit viruses (Douglas and Krüger, 2008) (Table 2). Control of this group in the Limarí basin depends on the correct taxonomic identification of the specimens found in the fields, a task that is not easy considering that many of these families are cryptic. In recent years, this problem has been tackled by molecular profiling of the specimens of certain Chilean populations (Correa *et al.*, 2012; Correa *et al.*, 2015).

The results have shown that 25% of the taxa recorded in the basin are species of quarantine significance for foreign export markets (Table 2). However, several species of these species are under control or have been eradicated from the Coquimbo Region and the rest of the country, such as the Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae), one of the major pests, whose larvae cause serious damage to fruits. Currently, the Sistema Nacional de Detección de Moscas de la Fruta (SNDMF [Chilean Fruit Fly Detection System]), under the direction of SAG (Servicio Agrícola y Ganadero), has the mission of confirming the eradication of this insect in the country and conducting control activities against the potential arrival of this pest in Chile (Lobos *et al.*, 2005), as was the case in March 2015 when five adults and a focus of *C. capitata* larvae were detected in the urban area of the municipality of La Serena (SAG, 2015a; SAG, 2015b). In that same year, SAG put an end to the Mediterranean fruit fly eradication campaign in the municipalities of La Serena and Coquimbo, declaring the area free from this dipteran (SAG, 2015c).

In a different front, efforts are still underway to control and eradicate the European grapevine moth *Lobesia botrana* (Denis & Schiffermüller) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae), a species of economic significance in Europe that arrived in Chile, Argentina, and California in the period 2008-2010 (González, 2010; Mutis *et al.*, 2014). Currently, the National Program for the Eradication of *Lobesia botrana*, under the direction of SAG, is conducting control and eradication activities against this insect in the Atacama, Coquimbo, Valparaíso, Biobío, and Araucanía regions, using pheromone traps (Mutis *et al.*, 2014) and authorized pesticides (SAG, 2016).

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It is estimated that 21.8% of the arthropods recorded in the Limarí basin may have positive implications for agriculture due to their role as biologic controllers (predators and parasitoids), pollinators, saprobionts, or mycophagists. Within this group, the most important species were *Parastethorus histrio* Chauzeau (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), a predator of *Tetranychus urticae* C.L. Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae), followed by *Hippodamia (Adonia) variegata* (Goeze) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) (Table 1).

In view of the increase in the distribution of agricultural pests, it is essential to incorporate predator insects able to reduce pest attacks on crops as well as understand the population dynamics of these controller species in the ecosystems (New 2007; Sorribas *et al.*, 2016). For the above reasons, more bionomic studies on pests are required as predictive tools to propose control actions against these organisms (González, 1981; López-García, 2011).

The expansion of crop fields towards dryland areas is a radical change in the landscape composition (Alcayaga *et al.*, 2013) that directly affects the richness of several arthropod groups, including pests and natural predators (Jonsson *et al.*, 2012; Inclán *et al.*, 2015a). Several authors have suggested that the increased extent of high-intensity agricultural systems may lower species diversity and the abundance of natural enemies (Macfadyen *et al.*, 2011; Lohaus *et al.*, 2013). Consequently, it is expected that the expansion of technified crop fields towards dryland hillsides will favor the colonization, establishment and population growth of some arthropod groups in the Elqui basin (Coquimbo Region) (Pizarro-Araya *et al.*, 2009; Zuleta *et al.*, 2009; Young *et al.*, 2010). However, it is yet unclear how the changes in the landscape shape the species composition and how the population dynamics of natural enemies behaves (Inclán *et al.*, 2015b), processes that should be further studied in the transverse valleys of the Norte Chico.

CONCLUSIONS

The majority of the arthropod species of agricultural significance found in the study area were insects, which shows the huge diversity of this group and the availability of habitats and resources in the Limarí basin to support them. A significant proportion (25%) of the taxa recorded in this area were species of quarantine significance, with some genera – mostly insects, e.g., Aleyrodidae and Pseudococcidae – being primary pests in several crops, mainly export fruits, that require constant control of their local population densities. We hope that the data presented in this paper serves to characterize the level of threat and benefit of the arthropods of agricultural significance in this highly productive basin of the semiarid region of the Norte Chico of Chile.

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Table 1: Records of mites (Arachnida: Acari) found in the Limari Basin (Coquimbo Region, Chile): the scientific name, the source, and their economic importance are indicated.

Order	Family	Scientific name	Source	Economic significance
Acari	Anystidae	Anystidae sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Boophilus microplus</i>
	Ascidae	Ascidae sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Lycoriella auripila</i> and <i>Ephestia kuehniella</i>
	Eriophyidae	<i>Aceria granati</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Punica granatum</i>
		<i>Aceria sheldoni</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Aculops lycopersici</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees
		<i>Calepitrimerus vitis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on grapevine trees
		<i>Colomerus vitis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on grapevine trees
		<i>Eriophyes erineus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Juglans regia</i>
		<i>Eriophyes sheldoni</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Citrus</i> spp.
		<i>Oxycenus maxwelli</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees
	Eupodidae	Eupodidae sp.	SAG	Predates on nematodes
	Phytoseidae	Phytoseidae sp.	SAG	Predates on Acari
	Ixodidae	<i>Rhipicephalus sanguineus</i>	LEULS	<i>Babesia canis</i> infection
	Tenuipalpidae	<i>Brevipalpus chilensis</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on fruit trees; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Brevipalpus obovatus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Brevipalpus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and ornamental plants
	Tetranychidae	<i>Bryobia rubrioculus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on apple trees
		<i>Bryobia</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on cereals
		<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Eotetranychus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on grapevine trees
		<i>Oligonychus ilicis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Juglans regia</i>
		<i>Oligonychus vitis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Oligonychus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on grapevine trees
		<i>Panonychus citri</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Panonychus ulmi</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		Tetranychidae sp.	SAG	Phytophagous
		<i>Tetranychus cinnabarinus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on tomatoes
		<i>Tetranychus desertorum</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on beans, cucurbits, and apricots
		<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and vegetables
		<i>Tetranychus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and vegetables
	Tydeidae	<i>Lorrya</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous

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Abbreviations: LEULS: Laboratorio de Entomología Ecológica, Universidad de La Serena, SAG: Servicio Agrícola y Ganadero.

Table 2: Records of insects (Insecta) found in the Limarí Basin (Coquimbo Region, Chile): the scientific name, the source, and their economic importance are indicated.

Order	Family	Scientific name	Source	Economic significance
Coleoptera	Aderidae	<i>Aderus</i> sp.	JEBC	Saprophagous
	Anthicidae	<i>Ischyropalpus curtisi</i>	SAG	Predates on Acari
		<i>Ischyropalpus</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on Acari
	Cantharidae	Cantharidae sp.	SAG	Predates on insects
	Carabidae	<i>Anisotarsus</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Inopus rubriceps</i> ; generalist
		<i>Callidula nigrofasciata</i>	SAG	Predates on insects
		<i>Calosoma vagans</i>	JEBC	Predates on Lepidoptera larvae; generalist
		Carabidae sp.	SAG	Predates on insects
		<i>Metius</i> sp. 2	JEBC	Predates on <i>Premnotrypes latithorax</i> (Curculionidae); generalist
		<i>Trirammatus striatula</i>	LEULS	Predates on Aphididae species; generalist
	Chrysomelidae	<i>Chelymorpha varians</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on Convolvulaceae (<i>Convolvulus</i> and <i>Ipomaea</i>) spp.; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Pachybrachis</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Baccharis</i> spp.; <i>Pachybrachis pallens</i> is a species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Phaedon semimarginatus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Baccharis linearis</i> and <i>Baccharis</i> spp.
		<i>Procalus viridis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Lithraea caustica</i>
		<i>Procalus</i> sp.	LEULS	Phytophagous on <i>Lithraea caustica</i>
		<i>Xanthogaleruca luteola</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Ulmus</i> spp.
	Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae	<i>Lithraeus egenus</i>	SAG, JEBC	Controls <i>Plantago</i> spp. weed; spermophagous; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Lithraeus elegans</i>	SAG, JEBC	Spermophagous on <i>Lithraea caustica</i> ; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Lithraeus leguminarius</i>	JEBC	Spermophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Lithraeus mutatus</i>	JEBC	Spermophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Lithraeus pyrrhomelas</i>	JEBC	Spermophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Lithraeus</i> sp.	SAG	Spermophagous on <i>Schinus</i> spp.; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Megacerus eulophus</i>	SAG	Controls Convolvulaceae weed; spermophagous; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Pentobruchus germaini</i>	SAG	Spermophagous on the ornamental <i>Parkinsonia aculeata</i>
		<i>Pseudopachymerina spinipes</i>	SAG, JEBC	Spermophagous on <i>Acacia caven</i>
		<i>Rhipibruchus picturatus</i>	MEUC	Spermophagous on <i>Prosopis</i> spp.
		<i>Scutobruchus ceratioborus</i>	JEBC	Spermophagous on <i>Prosopis</i> spp.
		<i>Stator</i> sp.	SAG	Spermophagous on <i>Acacia</i> spp.; <i>Stator cearamus</i> is a species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Stator tigrensis</i>	SAG	Spermophagous on <i>Acacia visco</i> (ornamental)
	Cleridae	<i>Corinthiscus denticollis</i>	JEBC	Predates on xylophagous species
	Coccinellidae	<i>Adalia angulifera</i>	SAG, JEBC, LEULS	Predates on <i>Myzocallis coryli</i> (Aphididae); generalist
		<i>Adalia bipunctata</i>	SAG, LEULS	Predates on Aphididae species
		<i>Adalia deficiens</i>	SAG, JEBC, LEULS	Predates on <i>Myzocallis coryli</i> (Aphididae)
		<i>Clitosthetus arcuatus</i>	SAG	Predates on <i>Siphoninus phillyreae</i> and <i>Saissetia</i> spp.

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		<i>Coccidophilus arrowi</i>	JEBC	Predates on Diaspididae
		<i>Coccidophilus transandinus</i>	JEBC	Predates on <i>Quadraspidotus perniciosus</i>
		<i>Cryptolaemus montrouzieri</i>	LEULS, SAG	Predates on <i>Planococcus</i> spp. and <i>Pseudococcus</i> spp.
		<i>Eriopsis chilensis</i> (nec <i>concinna</i>)	JEBC, SAG, LEULS	Predates on <i>Myzocallis coryli</i> and Aphididae
		<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	SAG, LEULS	Predates on Aphidoidea, insects and other coccinellids
		<i>Hippodamia</i> (<i>Adonia</i>) <i>variegata</i>	SAG, JEBC, LEULS	Predates on <i>Sitobion avenae</i> and <i>Metopolophium dirhodum</i> , generalist on Aphididae
		<i>Hippodamia convergens</i>	LEULS	Predates on <i>Anagasta kuehniella</i> (Pyralidae) and Aphididae
		<i>Hippodamia</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Sitobion avenae</i> and <i>Metopolophium dirhodum</i>
		<i>Hyperaspis nana</i>	SAG	Predates on Coccidae
		<i>Hyperaspis sphaeridioides</i>	SAG, JEBC	Predates on <i>Rhopalosiphum maidis</i> y <i>Acyrtosiphon pisum</i>
		<i>Olla v-nigrum</i>	SAG	Predates on <i>Diaphorina citri</i>
		<i>Parastethorus histrio</i>	SAG	Predates on <i>Tetranychus urticae</i>
		<i>Psyllobora bicongregata</i>	SAG	Mycophagous (predates on <i>Erysiphe</i> spp.)
		<i>Rhyzobius lophantae</i>	SAG, LEULS	Predates on <i>Aonidiella aurantii</i>
		<i>Rodolia cardinalis</i>	SAG	Predates on <i>Icerya purchasi</i>
		<i>Scymnus</i> (<i>Pullus</i>) <i>bicolor</i>	JEBC, SAG	Predates on <i>Aphis gossypii</i> (Aphididae)
		<i>Scymnus</i> (<i>Pullus</i>) <i>loewii</i>	JEBC, SAG	Predates on <i>Aphis gossypii</i> (Aphididae)
	Cryptophagidae	<i>Chiliotis</i> sp.	JEBC	Attacks stored products
		<i>Cryptophagus</i> sp.	SAG	Attacks stored products
	Curculionidae	<i>Acarapion ferruginosum</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous and carpophagous, feeds on <i>Acacia caven</i>
		<i>Apocnemidophorus obsoletus</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous
		<i>Apocnemidophorus pruinosus</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous
		<i>Asynonychus cervinus</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on fruit trees and grasslands; of quarantine significance in Japan
		<i>Cyldrorhinus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous
		<i>Geniocreminus angustirostris</i>	MEUC	Phytophagous; genus of quarantine significance
		<i>Gonipterus scutellatus</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on <i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.
		<i>Hyperoides subcinctus</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on vegetables and grasslands; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Listroderes bimaculatus</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous; genus of quarantine significance
		<i>Listroderes difficilis</i>	SAG, JEBC, LEULS	Phytophagous on vegetables; genus of quarantine significance
		<i>Listroderes</i> sp.	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on vegetables; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on vegetables and grasslands; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Naupactus xanthographus</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on fruit trees; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Platyaspistes venustus</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on fruit trees and vegetables; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Platyaspistes</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and vegetables; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Sibinia albiovittata</i>	JEBC	Of unknown biology; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Sibinia</i> sp.	SAG	Of unknown biology; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Sitona discoideus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Fabaceae; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Smicronyx argentinensis</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Sphenophorus</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on <i>Pennisetum</i> spp., <i>Cyperus</i> spp.,

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		<i>brunnipennis</i>		and <i>Juncus</i> spp.; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Strangaliodes</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous
	Dermeestidae	<i>Megatoma</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Naupactus xanthographus</i> (dead insect carcasses)
		<i>Trogoderma</i> sp.	SAG, JEBC	Attacks stored products
	Elateridae	<i>Antitypus insignitus</i>	JEBC	Associated with <i>Proustia</i> sp. and <i>Acacia caven</i>
		<i>Candanius gracillimus</i>	JEBC, MEUC	Predates on xylophagous larvae of Cerambycidae and Anobiidae
		<i>Conoderus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Elater abdominalis</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Stenocebrio coquimbensis</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous
	Erotylidae	<i>Loberus</i> sp.	JEBC	Phytophagous on <i>Puya chilensis</i>
	Histeridae	<i>Teretrius</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Prostephanus truncatus</i>
	Latridiidae	<i>Aridius</i> sp.	SAG	Attacks stored products; mycophagous
		<i>Cartodere</i> sp.	SAG	Attacks stored products (yeast); mycophagous
		<i>Corticaria</i> sp. 2	JEBC	Attacks stored products; mycophagous, feeds on spores
		<i>Melanophthalma</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Medicago sativa</i> pests; mycophagous
		<i>Melanophthalma</i> sp. 1	JEBC	Predates on <i>Medicago sativa</i> pests; mycophagous
		<i>Melanophthalma</i> sp. 2	JEBC	Predates on <i>Medicago sativa</i> pests; mycophagous
	Mauroniscidae	<i>Amecocerus</i> sp.	JEBC	Phytophagous
	Meloidae	<i>Picnoseus flavipennis</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous
	Melyridae	<i>Arthrobrachus flavipennis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous; host to Convolvulaceae, Asteraceae, and Geraniaceae species
		<i>Arthrobrachus limbatus</i>	SAG, JEBC	Phytophagous; host to Convolvulaceae, Asteraceae, and Geraniaceae species
		<i>Arthrobrachus nigromaculatus</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous; host to Convolvulaceae, Asteraceae, and Geraniaceae species
		<i>Arthrobrachus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous; host to Convolvulaceae, Asteraceae, and Geraniaceae species
		<i>Brachidia ruficollis</i>	JEBC	Phytophagous
		<i>Dasytes</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Lepidium draba</i>
	Nitidulidae	<i>Carpophilus hemipterus</i>	SAG	Attacks stored products and overripe fruits Pollinator
		<i>Carpophilus humeralis</i>	SAG	Attacks stored products and overripe fruits Pollinator
		<i>Carpophilus lugubris</i>	SAG, MEUC	Attacks stored products and overripe fruits Pollinator
		<i>Carpophilus</i> sp.	SAG	Attacks stored products and overripe fruits Pollinator
		<i>Cybocephalus</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on Diaspididae (Coccoidea)
	Oedemeridae	<i>Ananca</i> sp.	JEBC	Phytophagous
		<i>Ananca</i> sp. 1	JEBC	Phytophagous
	Ptinidae	<i>Lasioderma serricorne</i>	LEULS	Attacks stored products
		<i>Ptinus</i> sp.	SAG	Attacks stored products
		<i>Ptinus</i> sp. 1	JEBC	Attacks stored products
		<i>Ptinus</i> sp. 14	JEBC	Attacks stored products
		<i>Ptinus</i> sp. 15	JEBC	Attacks stored products
		<i>Ptinus</i> sp. 16	JEBC	Attacks stored products
		<i>Ptinus</i> sp. 20	JEBC	Attacks stored products
		<i>Ptinus</i> sp. 24	JEBC	Attacks stored products
		<i>Ptinus</i> sp. 25	JEBC	Attacks stored products
		<i>Stegobium paniceum</i>	LEULS, MEUC	Attacks stored products
	Scarabaeidae	<i>Arctodium vulpinum</i>	LEULS, Pizarro-Araya et al., (2015)	Phytophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Athlia rustica</i>	LEULS, Pizarro-Araya et al.,	Phytophagous on grapevine trees and a variety of roots

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			(2015)	
		<i>Liogenys palpalis</i>	LEULS, Pizarro-Araya <i>et al.</i> , (2015)	Phytophagous
		<i>Aulacopalpus castaneus</i>	LEULS	On topsoil, saprophagous and rhizophagous; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Aulacopalpus ciliatus</i>	LEULS	On topsoil, saprophagous and rhizophagous; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Hylamorpha elegans</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on grasslands and Poaceae (larvae)
		<i>Labarrus pseudolividus</i>	MEUC, LEULS	Detritivorous on cow dung
		<i>Lichnia gajardoi</i>	LEULS, Pizarro-Araya <i>et al.</i> , (2015)	Phytophagous
		<i>Lichnia</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous
		<i>Pacuvia philippiana</i>	LEULS, MEUC, Pizarro-Araya <i>et al.</i> , (2015)	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Tomarus villosus</i>	LEULS, MEUC	Phytophagous on grasslands (larvae)
	Scirtidae	<i>Cyphon</i> sp.	SAG	Saprophagous
	Scolytidae	<i>Pagiocerus frontalis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Zea mays</i>
	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta obscuripennis</i>	JEBC	Inhabits hydrophilic forests, xerophilous scrub, and spiny thickets, in the Fray Jorge National Park; saprophagous and predator
		<i>Baeocera</i> sp.	JEBC	Mycophagous
		<i>Baeocera</i> sp. 2	JEBC	Mycophagous
		<i>Oligota pygmaea</i>	SAG	Predates on <i>Oligonychus yothersi</i>
	Tenebrionidae	<i>Blapstinus punctulatus</i>	SAG, Pizarro-Araya & Cepeda-Pizarro (2013)	Phytophagous and saprophagous; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Blapstinus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on squash (<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>) and common sunflower (<i>Helianthus annuus</i>); genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Hypselops oblonga</i>	SAG, JEBC	Pollinator, saprophagous
		<i>Nycterinus rugiceps</i>	Pizarro-Araya & Cepeda-Pizarro (2013)	Saprophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Nycterinus</i> sp.	SAG,	Saprophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Nyctopetus</i> sp.	Pizarro-Araya & Cepeda-Pizarro (2013)	Saprophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
	Trogossitidae: Peltinae	<i>Diontolobus punctipennis</i>	SAG	Mycophagous, feeds on the spores and hyphae; adults are also nectarivore
		<i>Diontolobus</i> sp.	SAG	Mycophagous, feeds on the spores and hyphae; adults are also nectarivore
Dermaptera	Forficulidae	<i>Forficula auricularia</i>	LEULS	Attacks stored products Polyphagous predator and phytophagous
		Forficulidae sp.	SAG	Attacks stored products Polyphagous predator and phytophagous

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	Pygidicraniidae	<i>Esphalmenus lativentris</i>	LEULS	Omnivorous and detritivorous
Diptera	Agromyzidae	<i>Agromyza apfelbecki</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Cynara</i> spp.
		<i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables and ornamental plants
	Cecidomyiidae	<i>Cecidomyiidae</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on cereals
	Cryptochetidae	<i>Cryptochetum iceryae</i>	SAG	Parasitoid of <i>Icerya purchasi</i>
	Culicidae	<i>Culex pipiens</i>	LEULS	Anthropophilic hematophagous
		Culicidae sp.	SAG	Anthropophilic hematophagous
	Ulidiidae	<i>Euxesta eluta</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Zea mays</i>
		<i>Euxesta</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Zea mays</i>
		<i>Seioptera</i> sp.		Pollinator
	Syrphidae	<i>Eristalis tenax</i>	SAG	Potential transmitter of mycobacteria and vector of myiasis
	Tephritidae	<i>Ceratitis capitata</i>	SAG	Species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Euaresta</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous; biological control of weeds
		<i>Rachiptera</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Baccharis linearis</i>
		<i>Rhagoletis nova</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on sweet cucumber
	Tipulidae	<i>Tipula apterogyne</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on <i>Triticum</i> spp.
Hemiptera	Aleyrodidae	<i>Aleurothrixus floccosus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees; of quarantine significance for EPPO
		<i>Aleurothrixus porteri</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees; of quarantine significance for EPPO
		<i>Aleurothrixus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees; of quarantine significance for EPPO
		<i>Paraleyrodes</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Siphoninus phillyreae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Trialeurodes</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables and ornamental plants
		<i>Trialeurodes vaporariorum</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables and ornamental plants
	Anthocoridae	<i>Orius</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on Thysanoptera species
		<i>Xylocoris</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Tribolium castaneum</i>
	Aphididae	<i>Aphis craccivora</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees, vegetables, and ornamental plants
		<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and vegetables
		<i>Aphis spiraeicola</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees; transmits CTV
		<i>Aphis</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and vegetables
		<i>Brachycaudus persicae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous
		<i>Brachycaudus schwartzi</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Prunus</i> spp.
		<i>Brachycaudus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous
		<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Brassica</i> spp.
		<i>Capitophorus elaeagni</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Cynara scolymus</i>
				Species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Cavariella aegopodii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Apiaceae
		<i>Chromaphis juglandicola</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on walnut trees (<i>Juglans</i> spp.)
		<i>Dysaphis apiifolia</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Apiaceae
		<i>Dysaphis cynarae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Cynara scolymus</i>
				Species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Dysaphis foeniculus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Apiaceae, Brassicaceae, and Rosaceae
		<i>Dysaphis</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on Apiaceae, Brassicaceae, and Rosaceae
		<i>Essigella californica</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Pinus</i> spp.
		<i>Hyperomyzus lactucae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Asteraceae
		<i>Macrosiphum euphorbiae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Macrosiphum rosae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>
		<i>Myzus ornatus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Apiaceae and Asteraceae
		<i>Myzus persicae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and vegetables
		<i>Myzus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on Apiaceae and Asteraceae
		<i>Nasonovia ribisnigri</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Lactuca sativa</i>
		<i>Phoemyzus passerinii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Apiaceae
		<i>Therioaphis trifolii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Fabaceae
		<i>Toxoptera aurantii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Toxoptera</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on Dicotyledoneae

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		<i>Uroleucon</i> sp.	SAG	Production of pigments
		<i>Wahlgreniella nervata</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Rosa</i> spp.
	Cercopidae	Cercopidae sp.	SAG	Family of quarantine significance in the US
	Cicadellidae	<i>Empoasca</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Prunus persica</i> and <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> ; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Paratanus exitiosus</i>	SAG	Vector of yellow wilt
		<i>Xerophloea viridis</i>	SAG	Genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Xerophloea</i> sp.	SAG	Genus of quarantine significance in the US
	Cicadidae	<i>Tettigades lacertosa</i>	MNNC	Phytophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
	Coccidae	<i>Ceroplastes cirripediformis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Ceroplastes sinensis</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Ceroplastes</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Coccus hesperidum</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Parasaissetia nigra</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Parthenolecanium corni</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and ornamental plants
		<i>Parthenolecanium persicae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and ornamental plants
		<i>Parthenolecanium</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on ornamental plants
		<i>Saissetia coffeae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees
		<i>Saissetia oleae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees
		<i>Saissetia</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees
	Coreidae	<i>Althos distinctus</i>	SAG, MEUC	Phytophagous on Compositae and Bromeliaceae; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Althos nigropunctatus</i>	MNNC	Phytophagous on Compositae; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Leptoglossus occidentalis</i>	LEULS	Feeds mainly on pine trees, especially their seeds
		<i>Leptoglossus chilensis</i>	SAG, LEULS, MEUC	Phytophagous on blueberries, grapevines, hazel nuts; generalist; species of quarantine significance in the US
	Cydnidae	Cydnidae sp.	SAG	Family of quarantine significance in the US
	Dactylopiidae	<i>Dactylopius coccus</i>	SAG	Production of carmine
	Diaspididae	<i>Abgrallaspis</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on ornamental plants
		<i>Aonidiella aurantii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Aonidiella</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Aspidiotus nerii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees
		<i>Aulacaspis rosae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Rosa</i> spp. and <i>Rubus fruticosus</i>
		<i>Carulaspis minima</i>	SAG	Phytophagous
		<i>Diaspidiotus ancylus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Diaspidiotus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Epidiaspis leperii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Juglans regia</i>
		<i>Hemiberlesia lataniae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit, ornamental, and forest trees
		<i>Hemiberlesia rapax</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
		<i>Hemiberlesia</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit, ornamental, and forest trees
		<i>Lepidosaphes beckii</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Lepidosaphes ulmi</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Juglans regia</i>
		<i>Parlatoria oleae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees; of quarantine significance in Chile
		<i>Quadraspidotus lenticularis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees
		<i>Quadraspidotus perniciosus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees
	Dictyopharidae	Dictyopharidae sp.	SAG	Family of quarantine significance in the US
	Lygaeidae	<i>Geocoris sobrinus</i>	SAG	Predates on Heterocera (Lepidoptera) species
		<i>Lygaeus alboornatus</i>	SAG, LEULS, MNNC	Phytophagous on vegetables; of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Nysius irroratus</i>	MNNC	Polyphagous phytophagous; of quarantine significance in the US

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		<i>Nysius simulans</i>	LEULS	Polyphagous phytophagous; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Nysius</i> sp.	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on fruit trees and vegetables; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Oncopeltus miles</i>	SAG	Species of quarantine significance in the US
	Margarodidae	<i>Icerya purchasi</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees and ornamental plants
	Miridae	<i>Coridromius chenopodери</i>	SAG	Phytophagous, guest in Chenopodiaceae
		<i>Rhinachloa</i> sp.	SAG	Controls the weed <i>Parkinsonia aculeata</i>
		<i>Stenoparedra</i> sp.	SAG	Genus of quarantine significance in the US
	Nabidae	<i>Nabis punctipennis</i>	SAG, LEULS	Predates on Thysanoptera and Aphididae species
		<i>Nabis</i> sp.	SAG, LEULS	Predates on Thysanoptera and Aphididae species
	Pentatomidae	<i>Acedra albocostata</i>	LEULS, MEUC	Phytophagous; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Acedra fraterna</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on fruit trees; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Bagrada hilaris</i>	LEULS	Pest of quarantine significance (under control in Chile) Host mainly to Brassicaceae
		<i>Chinavia apicicorne</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on vegetables; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Euschistus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous
		<i>Nezara viridula</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Pentatoma dimidiaticollis</i>	SAG, MEUC	Phytophagous on wheat, barley, saltbushes, and alfalfa Species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Podisus</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Plutella xylostella</i>
	Pseudococcidae	<i>Chorizococcus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on grapevine trees
		<i>Phenacoccus parvus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Solanaceae; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Phenacoccus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on Solanaceae; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Planococcus citri</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Planococcus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Pseudococcus calceolariae</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees, vegetables, and ornamental plants; genus of quarantine significance
		<i>Pseudococcus longispinus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit, ornamental, and forest trees; genus of quarantine significance
		<i>Pseudococcus meridionalis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous; genus of quarantine significance
		<i>Pseudococcus viburni</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees, vegetables, and ornamental plants; genus of quarantine significance
		<i>Pseudococcus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit, ornamental, and forest trees; genus of quarantine significance
	Psyllidae	<i>Ctenarytaina eucalypti</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>
		<i>Glycaspis brimblecombei</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Russelliana solanicola</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Russelliana</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Trioza</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees; transmits citrus greening disease
	Reduviidae	<i>Empicoris rubromaculatus</i>	SAG	Predates on <i>Tetranychus urticae</i> and <i>Panonychus citri</i>
		<i>Zelus renardii</i>	LEULS	Generalist predator
		<i>Zelus</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on pest insects
	Rhopalidae	<i>Arhyssus tricostatus</i>	SAG, LEULS, MEUC	Phytophagous on fruit trees; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Harmostes</i> sp.	SAG	Genus of quarantine significance in the US

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		<i>Liorrhysus hyalinus</i>	SAG, LEULS	Phytophagous on sorghum; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Liorrhysus lineativentris</i>	SAG	Species of quarantine significance in the US
		Rhopalidae sp.	SAG	Family of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Xenogenus gracilis</i>	LEULS	Species of quarantine significance in the US
	Scutelleridae	<i>Misippus variabilis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Schinus</i> spp. and <i>Lithraea</i> spp.
	Tingidae	<i>Corythaica</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous; <i>Corythaica caestri</i> is a species of quarantine significance in the US
Hymenoptera	Aphelinidae	<i>Cales noacki</i>	SAG	Parasite of <i>Aleurothrix floccosus</i> and <i>Trialeurodes vaporariorum</i>
	Apidae	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	LEULS	Pollinator
		<i>Bombus terrestris</i>	LEULS	Pollinator
	Braconidae	<i>Lysiphlebus testaceipes</i>	SAG	Parasitoid of <i>Aphis gossypii</i> , <i>A. craccivora</i> , <i>Rhopalosiphum maidis</i> , and <i>R. padi</i>
	Encyrtidae	<i>Metaphycus</i> sp.	SAG	Parasitoid of Aleyrodidae species
		<i>Psyllaephagus pilosus</i>	SAG	Parasitoid of <i>Cenarytaina eucalypti</i>
	Eulophidae	<i>Ophelimus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.
	Formicidae	<i>Linepithema humile</i>	LEULS	Urban pest that causes serious ecological damage to agriculture and human health
		<i>Camponotus</i> sp.	SAG	Causes structural damage in wood
	Halictidae	<i>Corynura</i> sp.	SAG	Pollinator
	Ichneumonidae	<i>Diplazon laetatorius</i>	SAG	Parasitoid of <i>Baccha clavata</i> , <i>Mesogramma</i> sp., and Syrphidae
		<i>Ophion</i> sp.	SAG	Parasitoid of <i>Spodoptera</i> spp.
	Platygastridae	<i>Amitus spiniferus</i>	SAG	Parasitoid of <i>Aleurocanthus spiniferus</i>
	Pompilidae	<i>Pepsis limbata</i>	LEULS	Predator
		<i>Pepsis chilensis</i>	LEULS	Predator
		<i>Pepsis</i> sp.	JEBC	Predator
	Signiphoridae	<i>Signiphora</i> sp.	SAG	Parasitoid of <i>Pinnaspis minor</i> , Hemiptera, and Diptera
	Tenthredinidae	<i>Caliroa cerasi</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees (larvae)
		<i>Nematus oligospilus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Salix</i> sp.; species of quarantine significance in the US
	Torymidae	<i>Megastigmus transvaalensis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Schinus terebinthifolius</i>
	Vespidae	<i>Hypodynerus chilensis</i>	LEULS	Pollinator; predate on Lepidoptera larvae
		<i>Hypodynerus</i> sp.	SAG	Pollinator; predate on Lepidoptera larvae
		<i>Polistes canadensis</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous (causes damage to fruits)
		<i>Polistes dominulus</i>	SAG, LEULS	Predate on <i>Pieris rapae</i> (Pieridae)
		<i>Vespula germanica</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous (causes damage to fruits), entomophagous
Lepidoptera	Arctiidae	Arctiidae sp.	SAG	Family of quarantine significance in the US
	Coleophoridae	Coleophoridae sp.	SAG	Family of quarantine significance in the US
	Crambidae	<i>Achyra</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Medicago sativa</i>
		<i>Nomophila indistinctalis</i>	SAG	Genus of quarantine significance in the US
	Gelechiidae	<i>Phthorimaea operculella</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on olive trees
		<i>Symmetrischema tangolias</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Solanum tuberosum</i> L.
		<i>Tuta absoluta</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables; species of quarantine significance in the US
	Geometridae	<i>Cyclophora nanaria</i>	Vargas <i>et al.</i> , (2001)	Phytophagous on <i>Olea europaea</i> L.
	Gracillariidae	Gracillariidae sp.	SAG	Family of quarantine significance in the US
	Hesperiidae	<i>Hylephila fasciolata</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on <i>Medicago sativa</i> (larvae); <i>Hylephila signata</i> is a species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Lerodea eufala conceptionis</i>	LEULS	Pollinator, phytophagous
		<i>Pyrgus</i> sp.	SAG	Pollinator, phytophagous
		<i>Terias deva chilensis</i>	LEULS	Pollinator; phytophagous on <i>Senna</i> spp.
	Lycaenidae	Lycaenidae sp.	SAG	Pollinator, phytophagous; family of quarantine significance in the US

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		<i>Strymon</i> sp.	SAG	Pollinator, phytophagous
	Lymantriidae	<i>Orgyia antiqua</i>	SAG	Polyphagous phytophagous
	Nymphalidae	<i>Vanessa carye</i>	LEULS	Pollinator, phytophagous on Malvaceae
		<i>Vanessa</i> sp.	SAG	Pollinator, phytophagous
	Noctuidae	<i>Agrotis bilitura</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Agrotis lutescens</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Autographa bonaerensis</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Copitarsia turbata</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Faronta albilinea</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on cereals
		<i>Feltia subterranea</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables and cereals
		<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Peridroma saucia</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Pseudaletia impuncta</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on grasslands
		<i>Pseudaletia punctulata</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on cereals and grasslands
		<i>Rachiplusia un</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous on vegetables
		<i>Syngrapha gammoides</i>	Artigas (1994)	Phytophagous; of quarantine significance in the US
	Pieridae	<i>Phoebis sennae</i>	LEULS	Pollinator; phytophagous on <i>Senna</i> spp.
		<i>Tatochila mercedis mercedis</i>	LEULS	Pollinator, phytophagous on cruciferous vegetables
		<i>Tatochila</i> sp.	SAG	Pollinator, phytophagous on cruciferous vegetables
	Plutellidae	<i>Plutella xylostella</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on cruciferous vegetables; genus of quarantine significance in the US
	Pyalidae	<i>Ectomyelois ceratoniae</i>	SAG	Carpophagous on fruit trees; attacks stored products; genus of quarantine significance in the US
	Sphingidae	<i>Manduca sexta</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on solanaceous crops
	Tineidae	Tineidae sp.	SAG	Family of quarantine significance in the US
	Tortricidae	<i>Lobesia botrana</i>	SAG	Species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Cydia pomonella</i>	SAG	Spermophagous on <i>Malus domestica</i> , <i>Pyrus</i> spp.; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Epitonina aporema</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Fabaceae; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Epitonina orfilai</i>	SAG	Genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Proeulia auraria</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Proeulia</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees; genus of quarantine significance in the US
Neuroptera	Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysopa</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on Aphididae
		<i>Chrysoperla</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on Aphididae
		Chrysopidae sp.	SAG	Predates on insects
	Hemerobiidae	<i>Hemerobius</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Elatobium abietinum</i>
		<i>Symphorobius</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on Pseudococcidae
Orthoptera	Acrididae	<i>Dichroplus maculipenne</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on Poaceae; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Dichroplus</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on Poaceae; genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Schistocerca cancellata</i>	SAG,	Polyphagous phytophagous

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			LEULS	
		<i>Trimerotropis ochraceipennis</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on grasslands
	Gryllidae	<i>Gryllus fulvipennis</i>	LEULS	Phytophagous on avocado, citrus, and grapevine trees; species of quarantine significance in the US
	Tettigoniidae	<i>Cosmophyllum pallidulum</i>	LEULS	Attacks citrus fruits
	Tristiridae	<i>Elasmoderus lutescens</i>	LEULS	Polyphagous phytophagous
		<i>Elasmoderus wagenknechti</i>	SAG, LEULS	Polyphagous phytophagous
Phasmatodea	Pseudophasmatidae	<i>Bacunculus phyllopus</i>	SAG	Polyphagous phytophagous, <i>Muehlenbeckia</i> sp.
Psocoptera	Ectopsocidae	<i>Ectopsocus</i> sp.	SAG	Attacks stored products
	Liposcelidae	<i>Liposcelis</i> sp.	SAG	Attacks stored products
Thysanoptera	Aeolothripidae	<i>Aeolothrips</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Allium</i> spp.
	Phlaeothripidae	<i>Haplothrips</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Triticum</i> spp.
		<i>Liothrips</i> sp.	SAG	Phytophagous
	Thripidae	<i>Drepanothrips reuteri</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on grapevine trees
		<i>Frankliniella australis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on Fabaceae, Rosaceae, Brassicaceae, and Ericaceae; species of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Frankliniella occidentalis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables Transmitter of TSWV; genus of quarantine significance
		<i>Frankliniella valdiviana</i>	SAG	Anthophilous on <i>Baccharis</i> spp. and <i>Gochnatia</i> spp. (Asteraceae); genus of quarantine significance in the US
		<i>Heliothrips haemorrhoidalis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and ornamental plants
		<i>Limothrips cerealium</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>
		<i>Microcephalothrips abdominalis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees and ornamental plants (transmits TSV)
		<i>Scirtothrips inermis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on citrus trees
		<i>Scolothrips</i> sp.	SAG	Predates on <i>Tetranychus urticae</i> y <i>Raoiella</i> spp. (Tenuipalpidae)
		<i>Thrips australis</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on <i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.
		<i>Thrips physapus</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on vegetables and ornamental plants
		<i>Thrips tabaci</i>	SAG	Phytophagous on fruit trees, vegetables, and ornamental plants

Abbreviations: EEC: European Economic Community; CTV: *Citrus tristeza* virus; EPPO: European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization; TSV: tobacco streak virus; TSWV: tomato spotted wilt virus; Juan Enrique Barriga Collection (JEBC); Laboratorio de Entomología Ecológica, Universidad de La Serena, La Serena, Chile (LEULS); Museo Entomológico Luis Peña, Departamento de Sanidad Vegetal, Facultad de Ciencias Agronómicas, Universidad de Chile, Santiago, Chile (MEUC); Museo Nacional de Historia Natural, Santiago, Chile (MNNC).

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Fig. 1: Geographic location of the Limarí River basin (Coquimbo Region, Chile).

